

Rhenium. Part-XVII : A Few Complexes of Copper Containing Coordinated Perrhenate, $[\text{ReO}_4]^-$

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$[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ has been prepared from $\text{Cu}(\text{ReO}_4)_2$ and aqueous ammonia. $[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ has been obtained by reacting $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with aqueous pyridine followed by the addition of HReO_4 . Pyrolysis of the two complexes at 150 and 130° gives $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$, respectively. The kinetics of the thermal decomposition steps $\text{ML}_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2 \rightarrow \text{ML}_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2 \rightarrow \text{M}(\text{ReO}_4)_2$ have been studied from the TGA curves. Infrared and electronic spectral studies indicate that all the complexes contain coordinated perrhenate.

In continuation of our studies^{1,2} on the chemistry of coordinated perrhenate, we report here the isolation and characterisation of the complexes $[\text{CuL}_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ and $[\text{CuL}_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$, where $\text{L} = \text{NH}_3$ or py.

Experimental

Cupric carbonate and cupric chloride were E. Merck's guaranteed reagents. A solution of HReO_4 was prepared by passing a hot solution of KReO_4 (Degussa, West Germany) through a column of cation exchange resin (Amberlite IR-120) in hydrogen form³. A concentrated solution was obtained by evaporation of the effluent.

For the analysis of rhenium and copper the compounds were boiled with alkali. Copper was determined in the precipitate iodometrically. From the filtrate, rhenium was determined gravimetrically⁴ as tetraphenylarsonium perrhenate $[(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4\text{As}]\text{ReO}_4$. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method (in the ammine complexes) and micro Dumas' method (in the pyridine compounds).

Thermogravimetric analysis was made using a manual thermobalance. About 150 mg of the sample was heated at a rate of 2° per min. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out using a Guoy balance, $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ being the calibrant. The observed susceptibility was corrected for the TIP of ReO_4^- and the diamagnetism of ammonia/pyridine^{5,6}. Infrared spectra were recorded in Nujol mull from 4000 to 625 cm^{-1} using Perkin Elmer instrument (type 257). Reflectance spectra were recorded against magnesium oxide up to 1000 nm using a manual apparatus of Carl Zeiss Jena VSU2-P. The X-ray powder photographic plate was obtained with a Philips Norelco X-ray generator with CuK_α radiation operated at 30 kV and 10 mA. A Debye-Scherrer powder camera (dia. 11.46 cm) was used.

Preparation of the complexes :

$[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$: CuCO_3 was dissolved in an insufficient quantity of HReO_4 (obtained from 0.5 g KReO_4). It was filtered and the solution concentrated to 1 ml. Concentrated ammonia solution (2 ml) was added. Precipitate was formed immediately. After cooling for 1 hr, the product was filtered and recrystallised from warm concentrated ammonia (5 ml). It was washed with 50% (v/v) ammonia-ethanol mixture and dried in a desiccator over H_2SO_4 , yield 0.3 g.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$: This was prepared by heating $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ to constant weight at 150°. The loss in weight was 5.1%.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$: Freshly distilled pyridine (0.55 g ; 6.9 m mole) was added to $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.12 g ; 0.7 m mole) dissolved in water (2 ml). A clear solution was obtained on warming. A very concentrated solution of HReO_4 [obtained from 0.4 g (i.e. 1.4 m mole) KReO_4] was then added when a blue-violet precipitate appeared. On cooling in ice the mother liquor became almost colourless. The precipitate was filtered and dissolved in hot 10% pyridine (18 ml) containing traces of HReO_4 . The complex crystallised out on cooling in ice for 12 hr. It was washed and dried as in the case of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$, yield 0.35 g.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$: This was prepared by heating $[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ at 130° to constant weight. The loss in weight was 17.6%.

The analytical data and magnetic moments of the compounds are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The tetrammine and tetrapyridine complexes are blue-violet, while the diammine and dipyridine complexes are green. They all are microcrystalline,

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Fig. 1. Kinetics plots for the thermal decomposition of the complexes.

Compound	Analysis% ; Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} at 25° B.M.
	Cu	N	Re	
$[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$	10.0 (10.1)	8.6 (8.8)	58.3 (58.9)	1.84
$[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$	10.4 (10.6)	4.5 (4.7)	62.4 (62.3)	1.81
$[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$	7.0 (7.2)	6.3 (6.4)	42.0 (42.3)	1.90
$[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$	8.7 (8.8)	3.5 (3.9)	51.1 (51.6)	1.83

stable in air, nonhygroscopic and practically insoluble in water and common organic solvents.

The TGA curve of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ was recorded up to 325°. The compound started to decompose at ~140°. The curve gave two horizontals from 175-225° and 285-325° with weight losses of 5.1 and 10.5% (total), respectively which corresponded to the loss of 2 and 4 molecules of ammonia (Calcd. 5.4 and 10.8%, respectively). Isothermal heating of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ at 150° gave a loss of 5.1% and the residue analysed as $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$.

The thermogram of $[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ recorded up to 300°, gave a horizontal between 155-205° with a loss of 17.6% (calculated value for the loss of two pyridine molecules is 17.9%). A second horizontal

appeared above 280°. The observed loss in weight (35.7%) agreed with the loss calculated for the removal of all pyridine molecules. Isothermal heating of the tetrapyridine compound at 130° gave $[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ with a loss of 17.6%.

Attempts to determine the kinetic parameters for the decomposition steps $[\text{CuL}_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2] \rightarrow [\text{CuL}_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2] \rightarrow \text{Cu}(\text{ReO}_4)_2$ by the method of Freeman and Carroll⁷ gave straight line relationships (Fig. 1) in all cases, except $[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2] \rightarrow \text{Cu}(\text{ReO}_4)_2$. The kinetic parameters are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE THERMAL DECOMPOSITION

Decomposition step	Reaction order	E_{act} , kJ mol ⁻¹
$[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2] \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$	0.37	67.2
$[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2] \rightarrow \text{Cu}(\text{ReO}_4)_2$	0.47	44.3
$[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2] \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{py})_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$	0.35	67.2

In the ir spectra of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ (Table 3), the ν_1 mode of ReO_4^- appears as a weak intensity band and the ν_3 mode is split into two bands by about 10 cm^{-1} . The spectra of the two pyridine complexes, however, show a stronger splitting of the ν_3 band, while the ν_1 mode appears at 960 cm^{-1} as a medium intensity band (Table 3). Since pyridine does not give any

TABLE 3—IR SPECTRAL BANDS OF THE COMPLEXES (ν , cm^{-1})

Compound	$\nu(\text{NH}_3)$	$\delta(\text{H-N-H})$	$\nu_1(\text{ReO}_4)$	$\nu_3(\text{ReO}_4)$
$[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$	3400 m, 3280 m	1620 m, 1420 w, 1260 m	965 w	900 vs, 890 vs
$[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$	3250 m	1420 m	965 sh	910 vs, 890 vs
$[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$			965 m, 955 m	925 vs, 915 vs, 880 vs
$[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$			960 m	940 vs, 930 vs, 920 vs, 905 vs

strong band^s between 990 and 760 cm^{-1} , the ν_3 mode of ReO_4^- can be easily assigned in the pyridine complexes, although there may be some uncertainty in the location of the ν_1 band. Any idea about the mode of bonding of ReO_4^- (i.e. unidentate, bidentate or bridging) in the pyridine complexes cannot be formed from the ir spectra, as the spectra of these give three or more ν_3 bands. It is believed that $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ contain unidentate ReO_4^- , while $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ may contain bidentate or bridging ReO_4^- .

The tetrammine complex of copper, $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$, gave a well defined X-ray diffraction pattern. The d-values are presented in Table 4.

TABLE 4—X-RAY POWDER DIFFRACTION PATTERN OF $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$

$d(\text{\AA})$	Intensity	$d(\text{\AA})$	Intensity
6.51	9	3.08	5
5.99	9	2.92	8
5.34	10	2.46	2
4.99	10	2.25	3
4.70	8	2.17	3
3.90	8	2.07	3
3.62	10	1.84	3
3.43	10	1.78	7
3.22	5	1.61	7

The electronic spectra of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$ give strong and broad absorption bands near 16000 cm^{-1} and a shoulder in the low energy side (Table 5). The spectra of the other

TABLE 5—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compound	ν , cm^{-1}
$[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$	16000 ; 14000 sh
$[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_4(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$	15000 ; 13000 sh
$[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$	14000
$[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_2(\text{ReO}_4)_2]$	13000

two complexes give very broad bands around 14000 cm^{-1} . It thus appears that all the four complexes are tetragonally distorted Cu(II) complexes, i.e., they contain coordinated perrhenate.

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